

Quantum Free Particle $\exp(ipx)$ With p Being Dynamic and x Static Part III

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In Parts I and II, we focused on momentum and x . In this note, we wish to focus on energy and time. If $\exp(ipx)$ means that p (energy flow) is the same at every x , but at the same time one must have probability flow in a certain direction, one must have a two dimensional probability, with each component being periodic. The period is related to p , the flux. In a rest frame, however, (for a particle with mass), one only has energy which is a conserved quantity in time. By the same arguments made for $\exp(ipx)$, it seems that $\exp(iEt)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$ must represent the idea that energy should be the same at each t (where t is a math variable used for probability), but at the same time there must be an indication of flow or change in time, which occurs in one direction. This again requires two dimensions with each component being periodic. In this case, E (energy), governs the flow in time. (We suggest using $-Et+px$ because it is a Lorentz invariant.)

As a result, one again does not follow the particle in time. If one did so, there would be no probability. Nevertheless, the energy is flowing, so to speak, from one t to the next, just as p indicates motion of energy from one x to the next at a certain rate. As a result, we suggest that the uncertainty relationship which holds for p,x must also hold for E,t . It is possible to derive the uncertainty relationship for p,x using commutation and operators.. Once the result is found, we argue that it automatically applies to time. This seems to suggest that since one does not follow the particle strictly in time in a probabilistic approach, or in space for that matter, there can be uncertainty in both time and position, but for $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, there is no uncertainty in E or p .

Momentum and x

In Parts I and II, we used the classical $P(x)dx = dx/L$ (where L is length) and argued that it is equivalent to:

$$P(x) = P_d(px)P_d(-px) \quad ((1))$$

P and $-p$ must cancel and so one wishes to have a periodic function (not growing or declining indefinitely) so $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution. We argued in Part II that ((1)) holds because $P(x)=1/L$ holds for a rest mass which does not move. In fact, $P(x)=1/L$ does not need to be associated with motion at all. This suggests that motion must be accounted for in a $P_d(px)$ dynamical probability, not in $P(x)$.

The main focus of Parts I and II, however, was to try to interpret $\exp(ipx)$. We argued that p is a constant at each x and so from a probability perspective, one should have the same probability at each x . On the other hand, p implies energy flux and so there is motion in x and there should be probability flowing out in the direction of p . We argued that this appears to be a paradox, but a complex function with periodic components could describe a decrease of probability in one dimension and increase in another such that the modulus is constant. This implies that x is a static variable as considered in a probability function, but one cannot overlook the fact that there

is motion in space, i.e. there must be probability flow at the same time in one direction. This leads to the idea that even though p is certain, there is uncertainty within \hbar/p in space. This is not a problem in the probabilistic view because one does not follow the particle in space and time. In particular, $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ and $\exp(ipx)$ explicitly shows that one does not know v .

This idea can be generalized using $W(x)=\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. If each certain p has an uncertainty in x , then $W(x)$ has both uncertainty in p (due to the $a(p)$ s) and in x . In (1) one sees that an operator-commutator approach may be used to quantify this uncertainty, i.e

. $\Delta p \Delta x \geq \hbar/2$, ((2)) , where Δ is the square root of the variance

but also a wave-mechanics approach may be used. In the latter case, d/dx appears through integration by parts, not as an a priori operator of momentum ($-i\hbar d/dx$).

Even though ((2)) applies to p and x , it seems that if one considers E and t , there is controversy and different interpretations as suggested in (1).

We try to suggest here that the notion of a constant in space, namely momentum (energy flux) and the idea that there must also be probability flow in x (in the direction of p) creates not only $\exp(ipx)$, but also $\exp(-iEt)$. In both cases, one does NOT follow the particle in time-space and so x and t in $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ are math variables. Nevertheless, one cannot ignore the fact that there is change in both space and time and so must include probability flow. In one case, p is linked to probability flow in space and in the other case, E is linked to probability flow in time as we try to argue in the next section.

E and t

If one accepts that $\exp(ipx)$ means that one should have the same p at each x (it is a conserved quantity and there is translational invariance and one does not follow the particle in time), but at the same time there must be probability flow in the direction of p because there is motion in one direction, then one obtains $\exp(ipx)$. The wavelength is linked to the energy flux p and there are two dimensions because probability flow implies a change in probability in x , yet at the same time probability (or at least its magnitude) cannot change. One uses a periodic function for both components of $\exp(ipx)$ to account for this.

If this is the case, then a particle with rest mass would have no momentum, only energy. This energy exists in time, but in a probabilistic picture, one does not follow the particle in time. To do so is a deterministic approach. Thus, t is a math variable, yet physically the particle is at one t , then the next etc. It is as if it is flowing through time. We thus suggest, as in the case, of p , that one must use $\exp(-iEt)$ to describe probability as having the same modulus at each t and yet periodically flowing. We use $-iEt$ so that $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant. The main point we wish to make in this note is that by using a clock as a measuring device (just as a ruler and a clock are used for motion), the particle seems to be changing from one t to the next. In other words, it is moving in time (in one direction), yet it has the same probability to be at any time.

This is the same paradox which we argued exists for p and x . We suggest that $\exp(-iEt)$ resolves this paradox.

This seems to suggest that for a given certain p , there is uncertainty in x , because the particle tries to be at each x point to an extent, but there must also be flow. One does not worry about following the particle in time. In the same way, the particle moves in time, but has the same probability to be at each t_i . The combination is an uncertainty in time.

On average, if a particle moves with a constant speed, one has $x=vt$, but at a microscopic level, we argue that neither the time or x position follow $x=vt$ exactly according to a probabilistic view.

If ((2)) holds for p and x and the interpretation is the same for $\exp(-iEt)$, then creating $W = \text{Sum over } a(E)\exp(-iEt)$ should lead to the same relationship ((2)). Here $a(E)$ may be set to $a_1(E)W E(x^2)$ where $W E$ is the wavefunction of E . Here x^2 is some x point which one wishes to examine. In such a case, there is uncertainty in energy E , but each certain E has uncertainty in time and so there should be overall uncertainty in time and energy.

Conserved Quantity and Flow in X or T

The above considerations of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ deal with a conserved quantity, p or E . If followed in time, p changes from one x to another (as t changes) at a constant rate and E changes from one t to another. Given that the quantity p or t is conserved, it should be the same at each x or t , yet one cannot ignore probability flow because change occurs deterministically and must be accounted for even in the probabilistic scenario. In the case of momentum, there could be motion to the right or left (one dimension) and this is information which should appear in a probability expression for p and x . Removing information about p is like having p and $-p$ together or a rest mass. This scenario, i.e. $P(x)=1/L = P_d(px)P_d(-px)$ shows that probability flow must exist even for a conserved quantity which is the same at each x or t .

Interestingly, E seems to change from one t to the next and so should be treated in the same manner. Physically, however, no extra energy is given to E to make it move in time (unlike in the case of p , where m_0 (rest mass) must be accelerated. In fact, E only moves in time because a clock exists and one measures a change in the clock time (and then measures E again to see that it has not changed) and treats t as a space-time variable ct . Even if one did not have a clock, one could observe events which do not change E (i.e. one has to measure E again after each event) and write each event in a log, followed by a measurement of E . One would have a sequence of events, each with the same E and the events would suggest a dimension, we argue. It is the creation of this dimension (called time) which seems to give the appearance of E changing from one point to another. In the case of a clock, the events are equispaced and consistent. The mathematics of the apparent flow $\exp(-iEt)$ shows that E is a constant because it is not a function of time, nevertheless the probability flow nature is important because it ensures that:

$$\int dt \exp(iE_1t) \exp(-iE_2t) = 0 \text{ unless } E_1=E_2 \quad ((3))$$

One may, however, argue that this is a math property. Nevertheless, we argue that $\exp(-iEt)$ describes a flow of probability through time which is treated as a dimension through ct . The form $\exp(-iEt)$ is not simply mathematical, it suggests that there is uncertainty in time within a time period \hbar/E . Such results do not appear if one uses a deterministic Newtonian approach. One measure E at some time t and if there are no interactions, then one has the same E at a later time. There is no probability and so no probability flow in time. The particle may be said to move in time, but that simply means that it has the same E at each t .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argued in Parts I and II, that given a conserved quantity which seems to be linked to a particle dimension, e.g. momentum (energy flow) and x , one should have the same probability to have p at each x (probability does not follow a particle in time), but at the same time one cannot ignore probability flow due to the motion. This seems at first like a paradox. We argued in Part II that one must include probability flow because $P(x) = 1/L$ ($L = \text{length}$) from classical physics applies to a rest mass with equal probability to be at any x in L . Thus, one expects p AND $-p$ probabilities (product) to have equivalency with a rest mass. This implies a two dimensional probability $\exp(ipx)$. The modulus tries to account for p being the same at each x , yet there is probability flow in one direction.

Given that E appears at t_1 , but then again at t_2 etc, if ct is a dimension as it is relativity, then a rest mass seems to flow from t_1 to t_2 etc. Physically no extra energy is needed to create this flow, but it does seem to exist and so one again has the notion of the same conserved quantity E energy at each t , together with motion in one direction. This implies $\exp(-iEt)$. (We chose $-$ so that $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant). This, in turn, suggests that one must have uncertainty in time within a $T=\hbar/E$ time period. Presumably this may be measured (2).

References

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